

Machine learning for sleep quality analysis

Anna Fedorova, PhD.

University of Applied Sciences
Kufstein
Austria

2110837178@stud.fh-kufstein.ac.at

ABSTRACT

Sleep is an essential and fundamental process of human existence. Low sleep quality or sleep disorders can lead to the worsening of the overall health state, as it plays a crucial role in multiple physical and psychological processes in the human organism. Therefore, understanding health and sleep parameters, that define sleep quality, plays an important role in improving overall health conditions. Methods of machine learning extend the sleep researchers' toolbox with some novel approaches and possibilities. This paper sums up the main topics, where machine learning has contributed to sleep research in the last decades and describes an example of sleep quality modeling using both physiological and psychological sleep and health characteristics from an open-source dataset. The model is based on the measurements obtained with an actigraph and the potential of alternative devices for data collection is discussed together with the importance of this approach. Model performance and discovered correlations are described in the results section. This overview shows how machine learning techniques can be used to characterize sleep disorders, evaluate the risk factors based on daily measurements and monitor sleep quality.

KEYWORDS

Machine learning; sleep research; sleep disorders; sleep quality; support vector machines; k-nearest neighbors; Pearson coefficient

1 Introduction

Sleep is a complex physiological process, that helps to restore all major body systems, like respiratory, central nervous, circulatory, and musculoskeletal from the wear during daily activities. Sleep deprivation and low sleep quality were shown to have destructional short- and long-term influences on the human body.

Unpredicted and fast changing events in recent years expressed much pressure on our emotional well-being and were shown to contribute to overall stress levels and in particular to decrease sleep quality [1]. In this environment, it is particularly important to have tools to study our sleep as one of the pillars of a stable and healthy psychological state. Among all research approaches, that were developed over the years for the study of sleep quality, machine learning (ML) methods are recent adoption, but they have already proven to be a promising and versatile method to obtain reliable results.

A large part of sleep studies in the laboratory environment is made by polysomnography (PSG), which produces a lot of labeled electrophysiological data. Most tasks performed with these large datasets include pattern recognition and are until today mostly done with rule-based computer programs, prone to bias and human error. Advances in computational technologies, especially in

“big data”, can allow to optimize the processing of PSG data. Not only could ML technologies allow to recognize patterns beyond explicitly programmed rules, but it is possible to enrich PSG data with other patients' information and overall demographic data using data processing. This approach would allow an intersectional view to sleep disorders, that was never achieved before. So far ML algorithms were incorporated in some areas of sleep research and show optimistic results, making it a promising subject of study.

1.1 Sleep staging

PSG records different types of physiological data including the electroencephalogram (EEG), electrooculogram (EOG), electromyogram (EMG), and electrocardiogram (ECG). Traditionally these recordings are divided into 30 s epochs and scored visually to classify as sleep or wakefulness, and sleep is subsequently identified as one of 5 stages of sleep. This process can take between 2 and 4 h for a whole-night sleep recording of a single patient, is done manually and is error-prone and subjective, as even between specialists the agreement rate on sleep stage classification may be less than 90 % [2]. The time-consuming evaluation process and the requirement to spend a night in a specially equipped laboratory lead to long waiting lists of patients in need of this procedure. The introduction of a standardized automatic sleep stage recognition would significantly improve this situation.

ML allows to use huge datasets with heterogenous patient populations, to develop more generalizable algorithms and thus to overcome prior limitations of human-computer algorithms trained on small samples and to increase reliability. ML can employ additional metrics not used before to stage sleep and show unknown interactions of signal patterns and patients' physical parameters and respiratory dynamics. There are already multiple studies, that resulted in sleep stage with ML with accuracy over 80 % using artificial and convolutional neural networks, hidden Markov model, random forest or support vector machine classifier [3].

The disadvantages of the golden standard of sleep research PSG can be omitted by introduction of wearable accelerometers for sleep research. They were proven to be a valid alternative for PSG and classification of sleep stages using accelerometry data is done with some heuristic algorithms since 1990s. This type of input data can be also classified using ML. Sleep duration classification accuracy achieved with Random Forests and Hidden Markov Modelling (HMM) for accelerometry data was over 95 % [4]. Sleep staging did not show particularly high accuracy yet, but it can be improved with larger data sets used for training, which is not the case for heuristic approaches [5].

1.2 Recognition of sleep disorders

The need to perform PSG to identify sleep disorders creates a bottleneck and costs time for the patients. Using ML classifiers to predict the diagnosis with high accuracy may reduce the number of patients requiring the PSG screening. Eg. ML was shown to diagnose sleep apnea in multiple studies using different combinations of simple metrics, such as height, weight, BMI, age, sex, blood pressure, smoking and alcohol consumption. As shown in this review [6], the accuracy varies from 75 to 93 %, with most common models being logistic regression, linear regression, support vector machine, neural networks, and decision trees.

AI algorithms allow to recognize respiratory events, evaluate their physiological heterogeneity, and identify sleep-disordered breathing. Such measurements have been used to distinguish different types of apnea. This information enables early identification of patients at risk, risk stratification and even allows to anticipate adherence to treatment and choose a personalized treatment strategy [7].

Some types of hypersomnia present a diagnostic challenge with conventional methods. Recently it was shown that deep learning can be applied to diagnose narcolepsy and has the potential to differentiate narcolepsy subtypes. Beyond only relying on the established diagnostic criteria, ML can explore a mixture of clinical features and suggest new criteria [8].

ML has also been used to measure and predict circadian rhythms as well as document their disruptions. An important use case for this information lies outside of sleep health and may be a precise timing of cancer treatments based on AI estimates of circadian phases, which can improve the effectiveness of the treatment [8].

The use of AI in sleep research is not constricted to PSG or similar physical metrics. A very different approach was shown in [9], where natural language processing was used to analyse health related Twitter messages and extract causalities concerning insomnia and stress.

1.3 Alternative data sources

Actigraphy is known since 1995 to be a valid alternative to PSG to perform detection and analysis of sleep disorders, including insomnia and hypersomnia through recording and analysis of such metrics as the number and duration of awakenings, sleep duration, and time spent in bed [10]. All these metrics are derived from information about movement of a body part in single or multiple axes registered with a measuring device (actigraph), which is attached to this body part. In the subsequent data processing step the data is separated in epochs and those are labeled as sleep or wakefulness [11].

This method is widely used in different medical and research fields with the primary application for behavioral and mental disorders [11]. The study [12] was conducted on historic actigraphy data to prove its effectiveness for insomnia assessments. The authors could distinguish metrics to predict insomnia, such as sleep onset latency, total sleep time, wake after sleep onset, and sleep efficiency. Another study [13] compared PSG and actigraphy for the evaluation of chronic primary insomnia states, that actigraphy has a high potential for the analysis of sleep disorders and recommends it for concurrent use of supplementary assessment methods.

The emergence of Internet of Things made commercially available fitness and sleep trackers ubiquitous, resulting in a collection of multiple physiological signals over long

durations, some of them directly related to sleep. Analysis of the data from consumer sleep technologies (CST) allows estimating of sleep stages or evaluating sleep-disordered breathing based on sleep data recordings.

Such commercially available multi-sensor trackers as wristbands [14], rings [15], smart sleep monitors [16], were studied and compared with conventional polysomnography. The studies show high accuracy of the ML models based on these data and their use provide an important advantage comparing to the traditional medical equipment, because sleep assessment can be easily done while the patient is at home, sleeping in their usual setting and without the need to wear multiple sensors. Eg. comparing commercially available sleep assistant Somnify® against polysomnography (PSG), Somnify showed high accuracy of sleep vs wakefulness detection as well as sleep stage detection [16].

There were attempts to compare industrial CST with approved for medical research, eg. the study [17] compared the measurements taken with an actigraph with the Sleep Time App (Azumio Inc.). The App significantly overestimated the total sleep time compared to the actigraphy, however, showed no significant difference to self-reported sleep diaries. Also, there was no significant difference in sleep efficiency between methodologies, which is a promising result for CST as a source of information for sleep evaluation in research.

The role of CST in the practice of sleep medicine has not been established yet and needs deeper investigations, however, the growing number of peer-reviewed publications from the last couple of years dedicated to this topic shows a great interest of the research community some promising findings.

1.4 Current limitations of AI in sleep research

In general, AI has the potential to develop our understanding of sleep health, deepen our knowledge about sleep disorders and the aspects, that cause them, and broaden the range of tools to investigate sleep disruptions. However, sleep researchers must overcome some critical challenges before AI can be freely used in clinical medicine. The datasets available so far are mostly collected from subgroups, subsequently, they are not generalizable nor representative, and may be prone to bias. There is a strong need for the unification of databases gathered among international sleep researchers. Neither regulations nor standards exist for commercially developed AI algorithms, which also limits generalization. Due to the relatively recent implementation of AI in clinical practice, there is an acute need for policies of their use and additional guidelines for the security and storage of protected sleep information [7].

2 Methods

2.1 Dataset

The dataset Multilevel Monitoring of Activity and Sleep in Healthy People (MMASH) released under the Open Database License v1.0 and publicly available on PhysioNet is used as a data source [18]; [19]. It provides data from 22 young adults, combining physiological information, such as heart rate and triaxial accelerometer data, anthropomorphic characteristics (gender, height, weight, age), activity diaries, and answers to questionnaires about participants' psychological status.

Data was recorded for seven days, which corresponds with the Current Procedural Terminology coding requirements of the American Medical Association, in which actigraph data recording is considered most effective for a continuous period between 72 h and 14 days [20]. Table 1 shows the main actigraphy measurements used as independent variables in this dataset. Data was collected in cooperation between academia (University of Pisa) and industry (BioBeats Health Science Company).

Table 1: Context of independent variables [18]; [19]

Variables	Context
Total minutes in bed	Minutes spent in bed per night
Total sleep time (TST)	Length of sleep per night expressed in minutes
Wake after sleep onset (WASO)	Time spent awake after falling asleep for the first time
Number of awakenings	Number of awakenings during the night
Average awakening length	Time in seconds spent awakening during the night
Movement index	The number of minutes without movement is expressed as a percentage of the movement phase (i.e., the number of periods with arm movement).
Fragmentation index	The number of minutes with movement is expressed as a percentage of the immobile phase (i.e., the number of the period without arm movement)
Sleep fragmentation index	The ratio of the movement and fragmentation indices

2.2 Ethical consideration

The experimental participants signed official agreements after checking the study protocol, information on data usage, and risks (based on the General Data Protection Regulation: Regulation EU 2016/679 of the European Parliament and Council, 27/04/2016). This study was approved by the Ethics Committee of the University of Pisa (#0077455/2018).

2.3 Methods

Further only the data collected with Actigraph will be taken into consideration. Actigraphy data were collected continuously for 24 h from 22 young male adults, age between 22 and 40 years, weight 60-110 kg and height 169-205 cm. ActiGraph wGT3X-BT (ActiGraph LLC, Pensacola, FL, USA) is a triaxial accelerometer to record and to provide the physical activity of the participants. This device has dimensions of 4.6 x 3.3 x 1.5 and a weight of 19 g. Recording signal frequency ranges between 30 and 100 Hz. Accelerometers measure timestamped accelerations of the movement of the body part to which they are attached in g's in 1 to 3 orthogonal planes. Actigraph recorded such values as time, when participants went to and got out of bed, time of falling asleep, total sleeping time, time in bed, and the ratio between the last two; the number of awakenings, the length of awakenings, time with/without movements, the ratio between movement and fragmentation indices.

To describe sleep quality the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI) was collected for each participant to analyze

their sleeping patterns [21]. PSQI allows to classify sleep quality in a binary way – “good” or ‘bad’ and evaluation is based on the participants’ self-rating of seven sleeping characteristics. The sum of these components (subjective sleep quality, sleep latency, habitual sleep efficiency, sleep duration, awakening, sleep medication consumption, and daytime functioning) yields one global score, which lies between 0 and 21, with better sleep quality having lower values. “Good” sleep quality was assigned in the study if the score value was lower than 6. Previous research validated the efficiency of PSQI application for binary classification models, eg. to examine the association between sleep quality and depression symptoms [22].

2.4 Signal processing

To process actigraph data the Cole-Kripke algorithm [23] was used. This algorithm consists of three stages: resample recorded signal into 1 min epoch intervals; resample the epochs again with normalizing constant, which is calculated according to the following equation:

$$D(n) = C \sum_{i=-2}^4 W_i X(n-i) \quad (1)$$

where $D(n)$ is the output value and W_i is the coefficient of multiplication of the resampled signal epoch value and normalizing constant C . In the third stage output value from the stage 2 are rescored. This procedure allows to classify participants’ state into sleep/no-sleep.

The accuracy of actigraphic data for the sleep time ratio and latency were 82 % and 90 %. The Cole-Kripke algorithm can distinguish between states with an accuracy of 88 % and is effective for the given task both in research and medicine.

3 Analysis

The model described below was based on previous literature and proved to evaluate sleep problems with actigraphy and PSQI (Figure 2) [11]. Several machine learning models were tested: support vector machines (SVM), logistic regression (LR), K nearest neighbors (KNN), and Naïve Bayes (NB).

Figure 1: Model development process [11]

In the models actigraph data (s. Methods) are independent variables and the sleep quality according to PSQI is a dependent value. The performance of the obtained models was validated based on k-fold cross-validation with 3/5/8-fold cross-validation technique.

Additionally, the correlation between the sleep quality variable and each independent variable from actigraph data was tested using Pearson correlation. The significance level of 0,05 was selected. This estimation provided information about the contribution of each predictor to the classification model.

4 Results

4.1 Model performance

Table 2-4 show the metrics of four different models applied to the dataset separated according to the number of fold during cross-fold validation.

Table 2: Model comparison based on 3-fold cross-validation

Classifier	Accuracy	PPV	Sensitivity	Specificity
Logistic regression	57	60	75	33
Support vector machine	71	100	71	0
Fine k-nearest neighbor	81	100	79	100
Naïve Bayes	67	93	70	0

Table 3: Model comparison based on 5-fold cross-validation

Classifier	Accuracy	PPV	Sensitivity	Specificity
Logistic regression	62	60	82	40
Support vector machine	86	93	88	80
Fine k-nearest neighbor	76	93	78	67
Naïve Bayes	67	93	70	0

Table 4: Model comparison based on 8-fold cross-validation

Classifier	Accuracy	PPV	Sensitivity	Specificity
Logistic regression	67	80	75	40
Support vector machine	71	100	71	0
Fine k-nearest neighbor	81	93	82	75
Naïve Bayes	71	100	71	0

In general, the accuracy of models tends to increase with a higher number of cross-validation folds. It is visible, that KNN and SVM show the highest accuracy among assessed models showing accuracy up to 81-86 % depending on the cross-validation proportions. 5-fold cross-validation seems to work the best for the SVM, this model shows with 86 % the highest achieved accuracy among all models.

Other metrics, such as PPV, sensitivity and specificity tend to show heterogeneous results between 0 and 100 %. Low specificity values indicate the tendency of the model to predict a positive result giving a high number of false positives. Usually this is seen in combination with high sensitivity values, which is the case here. However, for two models with the highest accuracy they also reach very good values over 70 %, except specificity, and reach the

best scores with 5-fold cross-validation for SVM and 8-fold cross-validation for KNN.

4.2 Comparison of the results with other publications

These results correlate well with previous studies, that used the same open dataset for different binary classifications. The results shown here lie close to the results reported for KNN [24] and SVM [25] and can be considered as a prove of model performance in the described study. The accuracies of the cited models lie at over 90 % for [25] and over 77 % for [24]. Variation of accuracy can be explained with a different choice of metrics from the dataset used in the models. The other studies using SVM showed, that the model performance can be increased by application and combination of additional approaches, such as kernels and dynamically growing self-organizing trees.

The described binary classification model of sleep quality has shown satisfactory performance and demonstrated the efficiency of the MMASH dataset. It was already reported to show a relationship between various sensory data and sleep parameters. The study described here makes a successful attempt to establish a connection between objective sleep measurements and subjective metrics of perceived sleep quality. Questionnaires as PSQI allow researchers to build an understanding of the psychological component of the sleep result and correlate it with the physical state. Such studies can help to evaluate the reliability of questionnaires for sleep evaluation and bridge the gap between actigraphy sleep metrics and human perception of sleep.

4.3 Pearson correlation

The Pearson correlation showed “moderate significance” between 0.4 and 0.6, for two predictors: time in bed with a correlation value of 0.437 and awakening in minutes with 0.526. Time in bed can be a sign of poor sleep quality if the ratio between sleep duration and time in bed is low. This could be evidence of insomnia or problems falling asleep. The same is valid for awakenings – they can disturb sleep quality and be associated with insomnia disorder. These predictors have already shown potential for determining and solving sleep problems, as eg. [12]; [13] have shown time in bed, total sleep time, and the number of awakenings to be good metrics for insomnia classification.

4.4 Limitations of the study

The experiment group consisted of 22 young males with similar activity levels and no health conditions, mental or sleep problems. This homogeneous character of the testing group is a significant limitation for the generalization of results. To make the results transferable to other population groups it would be necessary to use bigger datasets that include more variations of anthropological characteristics.

Another possibility to improve the model would be to include other sleep questionnaires and go beyond the PSQI binary understanding of sleep quality (good vs bad). Combining the results from several sleep questionnaires would allow expanding the classification groups use din the model and deepen the understanding of the influence of different sleep parameters.

Also, it would be beneficial to repeat calculations with datasets obtained with other wearable devices, eg. include some of the most popular commercially available devices to see if they perform on the same level as the ones used in

the health research. The results of such research would potentially significantly extend the available data basis for sleep research and bring new insights about dependencies of sleep quality and various factors.

5 Conclusions

It was proven in previous research, that it is possible to show the relationship between sensory data obtained from different devices and sleep parameters. The described study confirms that machine learning methods applied to an actigraph dataset can offer an effective method to assess sleep quality.

Moreover, the study extends the link beyond solely objective health characteristics and includes subjective evaluation of sleep quality by participants, using the results of the PSQI survey as the metric for sleep quality. This linkage allows researching the dependence between physical parameters of sleep and their influence on the subjective well-being of the participants. Although actigraph delivers reliable data about the physical aspects of the sleep process, it can't assess the outcome the measured parameters have on the self-evaluation of a person. It was shown, that combining these data for processing with a machine learning algorithm can result in a model with significant accuracy and provide additional connections between physical aspects of sleep and psychological perception of sleep quality.

The sufficient model accuracy supports the suggestion, that wearable measuring devices can achieve high measurement quality and allow to obtain reliable sleep metrics outside of specially designated sleep laboratories. With the rise of commercially available devices that measure various sleep and health metrics, such models can allow to monitor the health state and sleep quality without the need of the disturbing experience of spending a night in a laboratory with multiple sensors attached to the body. It can also help to approach, track, and diagnose sleep problems in situations when immediate measurements in a hospital are not available due to dangerous political or environmental situations. Self-generated sleep-related metrics give an opportunity to collect data transcending the sleep laboratories.

REFERENCES

- [1] Haitham Jahrami; Ahmed S. BaHammam; Haifa AlGahtani; Ahmed Ebrahim; MoezAlIslam Faris; Kawthar AlEid et al. (2021): The examination of sleep quality for frontline healthcare workers during the outbreak of COVID-19. *Sleep & breathing = Schlaf & Atmung* 25 (1), pp. 503–511. DOI: 10.1007/s11325-020-02135-9.
- [2] Khalid Aboalayon; Miad Faezipour; Wafaa Almuhammadi; Saeid Moslehpour (2016): Sleep Stage Classification Using EEG Signal Analysis: A Comprehensive Survey and New Investigation. *Entropy* 18 (9), p. 272. DOI: 10.3390/e18090272.
- [3] Santosh Satapathy; D. Loganathan; Hari Kishan Kondaveeti; RamaKrishna Rath (2021): Performance analysis of machine learning algorithms on automated sleep staging feature sets. *CAAI Trans on Intel Tech* 6 (2), pp. 155–174. DOI: 10.1049/cit2.12042.
- [4] Nicholas Kuzik; John C. Spence; Valerie Carson (2021): Machine learning sleep duration classification in Preschoolers using waist-worn ActiGraphs. *Sleep medicine* 78, pp. 141–148. DOI: 10.1016/j.sleep.2020.12.019.
- [5] Kalaivani Sundararajan; Sonja Georgievskaja; Bart H. W. Te Lindert; Philip R. Gehrman; Jennifer Ramautar; Diego R. Mazzotti et al. (2021): Sleep classification from wrist-worn accelerometer data using random forests. *Scientific reports* 11 (1), p. 24. DOI: 10.1038/s41598-020-79217-x.
- [6] Daniela Ferreira-Santos; Pedro Amorim; Tiago Silva Martins; Matilde Monteiro-Soares; Pedro Pereira Rodrigues (2022): Enabling Early Obstructive Sleep Apnea Diagnosis With Machine Learning: Systematic Review. *Journal of medical Internet research* 24 (9), e39452. DOI: 10.2196/39452.
- [7] Cathy A. Goldstein; Richard B. Berry; David T. Kent; David A. Kristo; Azizi A. Seixas; Susan Redline; M. Brandon Westover (2020): Artificial intelligence in sleep medicine: background and implications for clinicians. *Journal of clinical sleep medicine : JCSM : official publication of the American Academy of Sleep Medicine* 16 (4), pp. 609–618. DOI: 10.5664/jcsm.8388.
- [8] Anuja Bandyopadhyay; Cathy Goldstein (2022): Clinical applications of artificial intelligence in sleep medicine: a sleep clinician's perspective. *Sleep & breathing*. DOI: 10.1007/s11325-022-02592-4.
- [9] Son Doan; Elly W. Yang; Sameer S. Tilak; Peter W. Li; Daniel S. Zisook; Manabu Torii (2019): Extracting health-related causality from twitter messages using natural language processing. *BMC medical informatics and decision making* 19 (Suppl 3), p. 79. DOI: 10.1186/s12911-019-0785-0.
- [10] American Academy of Sleep Medicine (2005): International classification of sleep disorders. *Diagnostic and coding manual*. 2. Aufl. Rochester: ASDA.
- [11] Olga V1 Bitkina; Jaehyun Park; Jungyoon Kim (2022): Modeling Sleep Quality Depending on Objective Actigraphic Indicators Based on Machine Learning Methods. *International journal of environmental research and public health* 19 (16). DOI: 10.3390/ijerph19169890.
- [12] Vincenzo Natale; Giuseppe Plazzi; Monica Martoni (2009): Actigraphy in the assessment of insomnia: a quantitative approach. *Sleep* 32 (6), pp. 767–771. DOI: 10.1093/sleep/32.6.767.
- [13] Børge Sivertsen; Siri Omvik; Odd E. Havik; Ståle Pallesen; Bjørn Bjorvatn; Geir Høstmark Nielsen et al. (2006): A comparison of actigraphy and polysomnography in older adults treated for chronic primary insomnia. *Sleep* 29 (10), pp. 1353–1358. DOI: 10.1093/sleep/29.10.1353.
- [14] Xuan Kai Lee; Nicholas I. Y. N. Chee; Ju Lynn Ong; Teck Boon Teo; Elaine van Rijn; June C. Lo; Michael W. L. Chee (2019): Validation of a Consumer Sleep Wearable Device With Actigraphy and Polysomnography in Adolescents Across Sleep Opportunity Manipulations. *Journal of clinical sleep medicine : JCSM : official publication of the American Academy of Sleep Medicine* 15 (9), pp. 1337–1346. DOI: 10.5664/jcsm.7932.
- [15] Massimiliano de Zambotti; Leonardo Rosas; Ian M. Colrain; Fiona C. Baker (2019): The Sleep of the Ring: Comparison of the ŌURA Sleep Tracker Against Polysomnography. *Behavioral sleep medicine* 17 (2), pp. 124–136. DOI: 10.1080/15402002.2017.1300587.
- [16] Ståle Toften; Ståle Pallesen; Maria Hrozanova; Frode Moen; Janne Grønli (2020): Validation of sleep stage classification using non-contact radar technology and machine learning (Somnofy®). *Sleep medicine* 75, pp. 54–61. DOI: 10.1016/j.sleep.2020.02.022.
- [17] Taylor Maynard; Erica Appleman; Alice Cronin-Golomb; Sandy Nearing (2021): Objective measurement of sleep by smartphone application: comparison with actigraphy and relation to self-reported sleep. *Exploration of Targeted Anti-tumor Therapy*. DOI: 10.37349/emed.2021.00057.
- [18] Alessio Rossi; Eleonora Da Pozzo; Dario Menicagli; Chiara Tremolanti; Corrado Priami; Alina Sirbu et al. (2020): Multilevel Monitoring of Activity and Sleep in Healthy people.
- [19] Alessio Rossi; Eleonora Da Pozzo; Dario Menicagli; Chiara Tremolanti; Corrado Priami; Alina Sirbu et al. (2020): A Public Dataset of 24-h Multi-Levels Psycho-Physiological Responses in Young Healthy Adults. *Data* 5 (4), p. 91. DOI: 10.3390/data5040091.
- [20] Association, American Medical (2017): *CPT Professional 2018*. Newburyport: American Medical Association. Available online at <https://ebookcentral.proquest.com/lib/kxp/detail.action?docID=6211833>.
- [21] Daniel J. Buysse; Charles F. Reynolds; Timothy H. Monk; Susan R. Berman; David J. Kupfer (1989): The Pittsburgh sleep quality index: A new instrument for psychiatric practice and research. *Psychiatry Research* 28 (2), pp. 193–213. DOI: 10.1016/0165-1781(89)90047-4.
- [22] Zhao Hu; Xidi Zhu; Atipatsa Chiwanda Kaminga; Tingting Zhu; Yu Nie; Huilan Xu (2020): Association between poor sleep quality and depression symptoms among the elderly in nursing homes in Hunan province, China: a cross-sectional study. *BMJ Open* 10 (7), e036401. DOI: 10.1136/bmjopen-2019-036401.
- [23] R. J. Cole; D. F. Kripke; W. Gruen; D. J. Mullaney; J. C. Gillin (1992): Automatic sleep/wake identification from wrist activity. *Sleep* 15 (5), pp. 461–469. DOI: 10.1093/sleep/15.5.461.
- [24] Duyan Geng; Zhaoxu Qin; Jiaxing Wang; Zeyu Gao; Ning Zhao (2022): Personalized recognition of wake/sleep state based on the combined shapelets and K-means algorithm. *Biomedical Signal Processing and Control* 71, p. 103132. DOI: 10.1016/j.bspc.2021.103132.
- [25] Matthew Oyeleye; Tianhua Chen; Sofya Titarenko; Grigoris Antoniou (2022): A Predictive Analysis of Heart Rates Using Machine Learning Techniques. *International journal of environmental research and public health* 19 (4). DOI: 10.3390/ijerph19042417.